

PURCHASE BEHAVIOUR OF MALE STUDENTS TOWARDS SKIN CARE PRODUCTS

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Abstract:

The competition in the cosmetic business is quite high, whether the economy is booming or in recession consumers still prioritize their skin. The purpose of this research paper is to determine the consumer behaviour and marketing mix factors influencing the purchase behaviour of male students in choosing skin care products. This was a quantitative research using questionnaire to collect data. The recommendations from the result suggest that the marketer must focus on manufacturing standard products with reasonable pricing and good packaging because the consumers are highly conscious about their skin. The result from the study could be a guideline to skin care products manufacturers to develop their product according to consumer needs.

Key Words: Skin Care, Cosmetics, Marketing Mix, Beauty, Purchase Behaviour & Brand Image

Introduction:

The eyes are described as the windows of the soul, the mouth as the courier of thought, and the nose as the servant of olfaction. The skin is just the frame to the picture. Unfortunately, many judge themselves according to this frame. They could either have feelings of content or censure of their own physical features. Many desire healthy looking skin that is smooth and firm. The attraction for this desire makes the market place booming with cosmetic industry in order to fulfil the consumers' desire. Most of people would like to be beautiful, healthy and good looking. Another important point which works in favour of this change in behaviour is that the global world we are living in sets stereotypes that become models. Models are presented widespread all around us in daily life such as on the television, in the commercials, in the magazines, on the billboard, in the fashion shows, in the streets and even at school or at workplace. This is a normal fact that most people want to look like the models.

While it is a common concern for women, it is just as important that men properly care for their skin as well. Because of this, a variety of products is available just for men and their skin and the men's beauty industry is growing explosively. They are using all kind of beauty products beyond shaving creams like perfume, deodorants, moisturiser, anti-aging creams, eye gels, hair gels, luxury facial cleansers, and Concealers. Skincare experts say men's attitudes towards beauty are quickly evolving as so-called traditional values appear to be in flux. "Men are no longer the only breadwinners, and gender roles are starting to blend," Millennial, who are increasingly exposed to powerful female figures, no longer associate beauty rituals with femininity, but rather with self-care and success but men have different expectations from their skincare products

Research Objective:

To determine university male student's behaviour towards skin care products.

Limitations:

This study has several limitations that should be addressed. Availability of a larger sample of sampling unit could improve the study further. Secondly there is a gender and age limitation. The findings of the study were confined to male aged 20-25 yr old As a result; generalizing the results reported in this research to other age should be done carefully.

Research Methodology:

This was a quantitative research study. The sample size was 400. The sampling unit was male students of age 20-25. Convenience sampling method was used.

Hypothesis

- The different personal factors affect male students in selecting skin care products.
- The marketing mix factors affects male students in selecting skin care products

Questionnaire was used as a tool to collect the primary data; the secondary data is collected from journals, websites, and magazines. The questionnaire was divided into three parts to collect consumer behaviour pattern

- In the first part personal data of respondents like age, occupation, level of education, money in hand was collected.
- In the second part the questions adopted evaluation of consumer behaviour theory on questions such as reason to purchase skin care products, how often they buy, budget to buy, place to buy, who influences their decision making. Closed ended questions were asked in this part.

- Questions regarding marketing mix factors were also asked like how do price affects their purchase behaviour, what attribute they look while purchasing skin care products, from where do they get information regarding products, does promotion play any role?

Data Analysis:

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences program (SPSS) version 15.0 was used in this study with a 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive statistics application was analyzed by finding percentage and mean, standard deviation for measuring the distribution of data used to describe the personal data along with description of results to analyze the characteristics of the various variables. Inferential statistics application was used for hypothesis testing, chi square and multiple regression analysis

The results from this study revealed that most of the respondents age were between 20-25 years, status was single mostly, undergraduate students, income was between 15,000-25,000 and they were spending 1000 to 2500 on skin care products, mostly they purchase from department store or online to choose a particular product, every 3 to 4 months, mouth of word advertising and sales promotion play major role. Their opinion was mostly influenced by product itself. A good product they were ready to buy any how followed by easy availability, good offers and at reasonable price

Discussions:

The different personal factors which affect male students purchase behaviour in selecting skin care products

Age:

Customers in different age groups have different needs and want. While people who belong to same age group differ in many other ways, they tend to share a set of values and common cultural experiences that they carry throughout life. In term of skin care products, younger generation tend to be more open to skin care products than older generation.

Income:

Income plays as an important factor in purchasing behaviour. People who have different income have different selection of product. Moreover, people who have high income are more ready to buy expensive products but people who have low income are not. Therefore, income is one factor that affects purchasing behaviour of skin care product.

Urbanisation:

It is one of the most important contributing factors that influence the demand of personal care products by men. As more and more people are changing their base and moving from rural to urban area they are more inclined towards fashion trends and corporate life style

Reference Group and Family:

The influence from group of people (friends and colleagues, etc.) or family is considered as an important element that affects purchasing behaviour, friends or family possibly convinced consumers into purchasing a particular product. Moreover, friends have an influence on men behaviour such as men will buy skin care products easier or take care more on themselves if they are encouraged and accepted by people who surround them.

Celebrity Endorsement:

Celebrity endorsement is one factor that affects on men's purchasing behaviour. It can be seen as a significant impact nowadays. They have tremendous effect on creative a positive or negative product

perspective. In term of skin care products, celebrities such as David Beckham and Brad Pitt have changed perception about men who use cosmetics.

Marketing Mix Affecting Purchase Behaviour of Male Students in Selecting Skin Care Products:

Product:

Product is any goods launched to a market for awareness, acquisition; utilizing or consumption and it suppose to be able to satisfy the need or want. Generally shaving products are accounted as skin care product for men, but it seems to be common and logical for male customers to buy and use those kinds of products. Consequently the term 'products' in this study refer to skin care products, excluding shaving products. The products for men cannot be served as same as women one. Almost everything should be particularly designed for the differences. The fact is that a facial skin of men is 22% thicker than women's by average because it's higher in collagen and elastic. Men's skin is oilier, tougher, and bigger prone and older look than the real age, that is first reason why men have dissimilar demand for the products from women's. Not only because of different skin type creating diverse demand on products, but the differences of personality between men and women also become main consideration creating dissimilar demand of product's quality, function, attribute and ingredient. For instance, as men usually spend time less in a bath room, the products have to be light textures in order to easily absorb. Additionally Men prefer the products which are invisible, fast penetrated, easy to use, less process, pleasant to put, less smells and with a proficient consequence (Hopkins, 2010). So it is reasonable that why 25 million men refuse to use a feminine product but they really seek for particular products designed for them.

Price:

'The price-fixing' is the most difficult part for a marketer. The companies have to fix the selling price of products considering many factors in the market like fixated price is still in a price range related to supply and demand while the buyers make a decision how much they are willing to pay for products, the selling price that the company set for the products must relate to the production's cost, the quality or attribute of products, the product ingredient, the positioning aspect, product brand, the evaluation of competition, the customer perception and the value toward the products.. Price can act as a differentiating agent for products and brand image provided by the companies comparing each others in the skin care market against men's customer mind. In addition to the relationship between price and men's customer, price is a big influence on buying decision making. More than 50 percents of all male respondents answered that price had either "high" or "very high" impact on their product purchasing. This result was a significantly higher response rate than other factors, even though "ease of use" or "habit/preferred brand" are realized as the important factors in men perspectives as well.

Place:

In general, the word 'place' in marketing mix strategy refers to how the products would make accessible to the customers. What products the company is selling, can directly affect on how the products should be distributed, and it chiefly impacts the production of products or service. For example for a small company, the appropriate position in the distribution system is at the end of the chain because a company is providing an assortment of products directly to the customer. In a relation with the male skin care market, there is a choice of channels in order to distribute the products to the customers through cosmetic counter, convenience store, super store, perfumery & drug store, direct sale and internet.

Promotion:

Promotion is the way of communicating with the customers in order to attract and establish the customer's demand and consumption. The main issues related to promotion are; branding: building a trademark or identification of a distinctive image to the products. During the intensive competition in many markets, the word 'brand' is primarily considered as main element as competitive advantage to differentiate it from others if the company has reputed brand as a commercial application. Besides, brand name communicates product image which connect to certain values. So the name should correspond to its positioning .As the product name, branding the products with a masculine implication or right word can content men customers not to feel ashamed toward their consumption. For example, naming the products by traditional way as a clear and simple word (as Clarins) or emphasizing on male name as Nickel should be considered. This consideration of promoting male name in the products can stimulate men for their use and consumption. Advertising: it is one of promotional activity to inform and activate the public in order to rise up the product sales. There are many forms of these promotions such as press, television, internet, sponsoring, public relation and sale promotions regarding men's skin care market, the marketers have to consider whom you are targeting and what you want to communicate? Therefore the messages should promote about personal hygiene, improving the skin, anti aging, solving skin problems, attractiveness, good looking, self confidence or even modern trends.

Conclusion:

The study had concluded with the following details; the marketing mixed factors affected male university students on selecting skin care products revealed that the product aspect was considered highly by the respondents, they look for good brand, better quality, good packaging, variety of aroma in a product .in case of price they look for appropriate price as they have so many options to choose from if price does not suits them.

So, reasonable pricing is another important factor for their purchase. They usually buy products which are easily available in shops or online. In case of marketing promotion advertising on television, free samples, salesperson and word of mouth advertising plays a major role. Now, men are comfortable buying and using skin care product in comparison to earlier times. It might be seen that skin care for men become more important in beauty care industry because skin care products are not seen as something that has been launched only for women anymore. Using skin care product can be seen as one way to take care of them.

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